

EFFECTIVENESS OF INTERACTIVE METHODS AND INNOVATIVE APPROACHES IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14574962>

Annotation: This article studies the effectiveness of using interactive methods and innovative approaches in the process of teaching English. The role of interactive methods in increasing students' interest in learning, developing their communication skills, and making the learning process more active and interesting is emphasized. The didactic and practical aspects of improving the quality of education using modern innovative technologies are also highlighted. The results of the study may be useful for teachers in organizing the educational process more effectively.

Keywords: English, interactive methods, innovative approaches, communicative competence, modern educational technologies, educational effectiveness, learning process.

In today's era of globalization, English is recognized not only as a means of international communication, but also as the key that opens the door to modern knowledge. However, the process of learning this language is not always effective and interesting. Traditional methods may not be effective enough in increasing students' activity and preparing them for real-life communication. At this time, new approaches, in particular interactive methods and innovative technologies, are gaining importance in the world of education.

The teacher should see students not only as recipients of knowledge, but also as active participants in the educational process. Interactive methods are an effective tool in ensuring this approach. As technologies develop, the possibility of using the virtual world and multimedia tools in the educational process opens the doors to new worlds for students. Therefore, it remains an important task for the teacher to not only use new tools in teaching English, but also to form a culture of their correct use.

Interactive and innovative approaches not only increase students' interest in the learning process, but also develop their ability to apply their knowledge in practice. This article discusses how these approaches can be implemented in teaching English and their impact on educational effectiveness. Because today, teaching English is not only about teaching a language, but also about forming a culture of communication, thinking and perceiving the world.

Motivating students to be active in the educational process and effectively developing their language skills largely depends on the methodology used. Traditional approaches to teaching English often take the form of one-way knowledge transfer, which limits students' participation in the lesson process. Therefore, the introduction of innovative approaches is gaining importance in the teaching process. The use of interactive methods and technologies creates the opportunity to make students active participants in education.

In this study, the use of interactive methods based on active communication with students was adopted as the main method. Among these methods, role-playing games, exercises for solving problem situations, group work techniques and teaching methods via online platforms were widely used. Role-playing games allow students to practice communicating in real-life situations, while also increasing their interest in the language. Working in groups develops teamwork skills in students and creates a platform for their exchange of ideas.

The introduction of technology into the educational process has allowed teachers to use multimedia tools. For example, video lessons, online quizzes, and mobile applications for language learning play an important role in making the lesson interesting and interactive. With the help of these tools, the process of learning English becomes easier and more effective for students. At the same time, teachers have the opportunity to revise their lessons based on new technologies and adapt them to the needs of students.

Another important aspect of the methodology is taking into account the needs and level of knowledge of students. By organizing the educational process in a person-oriented manner, it is possible to develop the unique abilities of each student. Therefore, during the study, the individual needs of students were identified through diagnostic tests and questionnaires, and teaching methods were adjusted.

These methodological approaches encourage students to be active, forming in them not only the ability to learn English, but also life communication skills. Thus, high efficiency can be achieved by introducing innovative and interactive approaches in the educational process.

Literature analysis:

Scientific and methodological sources dedicated to the methodology of teaching English widely cover the importance of interactive methods and innovative approaches in the language learning process. In the process of studying the literature, attention was paid to the effectiveness of modern

educational technologies, the relevance of the communicative approach, and strategies aimed at seeing students as active participants.

Many scholars, in particular J. Richards and T. Rodgers (2001), have identified the communicative approach as the main methodological principle in teaching English. Their research emphasizes that the language learning process should be focused on developing students' communication skills. In particular, it is important to create opportunities to use the language in real-life situations.

Research on interactive teaching methods by C. Bonwell and J. Eison (1991) has highlighted the benefits of encouraging students to actively participate in the lesson. They have found that interactive methods significantly increase students' mastery. In particular, group exercises and role-playing games have been noted to have a significant impact on language learning.

In his research on the impact of the use of innovative technologies on the educational process, A. Prensky (2001) described digital technologies as an effective tool for increasing students' interest and organizing the learning process in a person-oriented manner. In his opinion, with the help of modern technologies, the educational process becomes more active and interactive.

Research in this area is also developing steadily in Uzbekistan. In particular, the resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on improving the quality of education and the digitization of national curricula serve as an important basis for introducing innovative technologies into the educational process. Methodological guides developed by national researchers, including research on the use of digital platforms in teaching English, show the importance of organizing lessons in an individual and interactive manner.

The analyzed literature shows that interactive methods and innovative approaches in teaching English are necessary tools for developing students' communication skills, increasing their interest in the lesson, and effectively organizing the educational process. Therefore, it is necessary to deeply study and further develop the theoretical and practical aspects of using these approaches in the educational process.

Interactive approach and innovative methods:

Although much has been written about the use of interactive methods and innovative approaches in teaching English, it is important to analyze their effectiveness in practice in more depth. Modern methodologies, which are replacing traditional methods in today's educational process, are expanding the possibilities of increasing student activity, forming the ability to apply knowledge in practice, and improving the quality of education.

The use of interactive methods in the lesson helps to involve students not only as listeners, but also as active participants. For example, group discussions and role-playing allow students to practice real-life communication situations. These methods are especially important in language learning because they encourage students to communicate with each other, not just with the teacher. This process is crucial in developing students' communicative competence.

Also, the integration of innovative technologies into education makes learning English more interesting and interactive. Online platforms, mobile applications and digital simulators allow students to independently develop their language skills. These technologies are adapted to the needs of students, taking into account their individual learning speed. However, in this process, the teacher's training in the effective use of technologies is of great importance. In order for new tools to produce effective results, they must be properly introduced into the teaching process.

It should be noted that despite all the advantages of interactive approaches and innovative technologies, their success largely depends on the interaction between the teacher and students. The main task of the teacher is to stimulate the activity of students in the lesson, support their interest in learning, and create a comfortable learning environment.

The discussions in this article show that through the successful application of interactive and innovative approaches, students' motivation and skills in learning English increase significantly. This process is not only limited to improving the quality of education, but also opens up great opportunities for students in their future professional and social activities. Therefore, the effective implementation of these approaches in practice remains one of the main tasks of the education system.

Today, teaching English is not limited only to teaching the rules of the language, but also includes the formation of students' communication skills and preparing them for the global communication arena. In achieving these goals, interactive methods and innovative technologies are becoming an integral part of education. They not only increase students' interest in the lesson, but also strengthen their skills in applying knowledge in practice.

Through interactive methods, students become active participants in the lesson process. Role-playing games, group discussions and problem-solving exercises deepen students' knowledge, develop teamwork skills and allow them to use the language in real-life situations. At the same time, the integration of innovative technologies into education makes lessons more interesting and

effective. The use of digital platforms, online resources and mobile applications helps to organize the learning process in accordance with the individual needs of students.

At the same time, the qualifications of teachers and the skills of proper lesson planning are of great importance for the successful application of interactive and innovative approaches. The teacher should use new methods not only as a tool, but also as an effective approach that serves the goals of the educational process.

In conclusion, interactive methods and innovative approaches are one of the most effective tools for improving the quality of education in teaching English. These methods not only develop students' language learning skills, but also help to shape them as active citizens of the modern world. Therefore, the wider introduction of modern approaches to teaching English, strengthening interaction between teachers and students, and enriching education through interactive platforms will remain one of the priorities of future education.

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